

Electromyographical Analysis of Biceps Brachii During Eccentric and Concentric Contraction at Various Intensities

Dr. Amar Kumar¹ and Dr. Satpal Yadav²

¹Assistant Professor, LNIPE, Gwalior

²Assistant Professor, LNIPE, Guwahati

Abstract

In the modern era every sports scientist, coaches, trainer are trying for maximum performance by trying any means and methods. In this study we tried to determine the amplitude of EMG signal during eccentric contraction and concentric contraction at various intensities. So that we are able to prescribe the exercise to enhance the power of the muscles. Five male subjects were taken from Lakshmi Bai National University of Physical Education, Gwalior as a subject and had no injury in bone and also in upper extremity. Electrodes were placed on biceps parallel to the muscle fiber following the guidelines of SENIAM. Myoelectric signal was recorded using surface electrodes with the help of the instrument Bio Thought Technology of Eight Channels. The data were recorded in micro-volt (μV). The skin was prepared by shaving and cleansing to reduce impedance levels ($\leq 10 \text{ k}\Omega$). Biometrics SX230 active (Ag/AgCl) bipolar pre-amplified disc electrodes (Gain x 1000; Input impedance $> 100 \text{ M}\Omega$; common mode rejection ratio $> 96 \text{ dB}$; noise 1–2 $\mu\text{V rms}$; bandwidth 20–450 Hz) with a 1 cm separation distance were adhered parallel with the muscle fibers. The data were collected of each selected muscles during maximum isometric voluntary contraction. Each subject had performed 1 RM test for maximum strength of biceps muscles to decide the various intensity. The concentric and eccentric movements were performed by each subject after placement of electrode on biceps muscles at various intensities i.e., 70% of max, 80% of max and 90% of max in the fitness center of LNIPE, Gwalior. The finding revealed that EMG signal did not showed any significant difference during eccentric and concentric contraction. Garner *et al.* (2006) also showed that muscle contraction loaded in either eccentric or concentric contraction elicits a similar amplitude of EMG signal.

Keywords

Electromyography, Eccentric, Concentric

1. INTRODUCTION

Electromyography (EMG) is the study of muscle function through analysis of the electrical signals emanated during muscular contractions. Lippold and Bigland demonstrated that during a voluntary contraction, the tension is proportional to the measurable electrical activity under isometric contractions (Basmajain, 1967; Bigland and Lippold, 1954; Bigland *et al.*, 1953; Lippold. Furthermore, Bigland and Lippold (1954) reported that graded increases in contractile force are predominantly a result of an increase in the number of active motor units. Numerous studies have been conducted comparing EMG amplitude and motor unit activity during maximal and sub-maximal concentric (shortening) and eccentric (lengthening) contractions, with the bulk reporting lesser EMG amplitude and motor unit activation during eccentric contractions (Enoka, 1996; Grabiner and Owings, 2002; Grabiner

et al., 1995; Kay *et al.*, 2000; Madeleine *et al.*, 2001; Moritani *et al.*, 1987; Westing *et al.*, 1991). For example, Moritani and colleagues reported greater mean motor unit activation in concentric biceps brachii contractions compared to eccentric biceps brachii muscle actions. Although numerous studies support the concept that eccentric contractions elicit lesser motor unit activation and, in turn, lower EMG amplitudes compared to concentric contractions, we are not aware of any studies that have compared different loading mechanisms for eliciting isometric contractions (i.e. concentrically loaded versus eccentrically loaded). The purposes of this study was to check the EMG contraction level during eccentric contraction and concentric contraction at various intensities.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Participants and Variables

Five students of the Lakshmibai National University of Physical Education, Gwalior were selected as subjects for the study by employing purposive sampling.

The age level of the subjects ranged from eighteen to twenty four years. Players had represented inter university level and had no upper extremity injuries or any bone or joint disparities within the past years. By reviewing the literature and consultation with experts, the research scholar carried out an intensive study and selected major muscles. The Biceps Muscles were selected as a variable for this study.

3. PROCEDURE

The data for the selected muscle were obtained with the help of the instrument Bio Thought Technology of Eight Channels. The data were recorded in micro-volt (μv). The skin was prepared by shaving and cleansing to reduce impedance levels ($\leq 10 \text{ k}\Omega$). Biometrics SX230 active (Ag/AgCl) bipolar pre-amplified disc electrodes (Gain $\times 1000$; Input impedance $> 100 \text{ M}\Omega$; common mode rejection ratio $> 96 \text{ dB}$; noise $1\text{--}2 \mu\text{V rms}$; bandwidth $20\text{--}450 \text{ Hz}$) with a 1 cm separation distance were adhered parallel with the muscle fibers, The data were collected of each selected muscles during maximum isometric voluntary contraction. Each subject had performed 1 RM test for maximum strength of biceps muscles to decide the various intensity. Before the actual testing, the subjects were given a complete demonstration of each test and the purpose of the test was explained in details. After the demonstration and explanation, electrodes were placed in a proper manner and then subjects were allowed to practice trials in order to get familiarized with the test. On the day of testing each subjects were oriented to the testing protocol. The protocol was sequenced as mentioned below:

- Warm-up
- Electrode placement
- Practice and familiarization
- Exercise protocol.

3.1. Warm-up

Proper time was given to the subjects for general warm-up as well as for specific warm-up to avoid the injury.

3.2. Electrode Placement

Site preparation for the electrode-interface included shaving of the area, followed by abrasion using an alcohol soaked pad, rubbing the site of electrode application vigorously. A slight abrasive pad was used. The skin

preparation elicits a slight histochemical effect. Electrodes were placed according to the guidelines of SENIAM and reference electrodes were placed around the Table.

3.3. Practice and Familiarization

Sufficient practices were given for the better performance, so that they can understand the concept of movement.

3.4. Exercise Protocol

The concentric and eccentric movements were performed by each subject after placement of electrode on biceps muscles at various intensities i.e., 70% of max, 80% of max and 90% of max in the fitness center of LNIPE, Gwalior (Figure 1).

Figure 1

4. FINDINGS

For the analysis of electromyographic contraction during concentric and eccentric movement descriptive statistic and paired t-test were used at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Paired t-test of Electrical Activity of Biceps Muscles at Various Intensities During Eccentric and Concentric Contraction

S. No.	Intensity	Eccentric	Concentric	't'-test	'p'-value
1.	70% of Max	416.38	398.43	0.762	0.488
2.	80% of Max	513.66	508.62	0.770	0.484
3.	90% of Max	610.77	611.62	0.171	0.872

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study clearly revealed that electrical activity of biceps muscles during concentric contraction and eccentric contraction at various intensity i.e., of 60% of maximum strength, 70% of maximum strength, 90% of maximum strength did not showed any significant difference. There are two major theories regarding the origin of differences noted between concentric and eccentric muscle actions. The decreased EMG amplitude during eccentric muscle contractions is thought to be due to the greater overall musculotendinous force produced with lengthening contractions. Kossev and Christova (1998) as well as Laidlaw *et al.* (2000), both using indwelling electrodes, have shown that the number of motor units recruited is less and that the discharge rate is decreased in eccentric contractions compared to concentric contractions.

Obtaining MVIC using Eccentric methods is far more complex from an experimental perspective, and presents several more limitations than Concentric. During Concentric contractions, the MVIC value is readily obtainable due to the fact that the participant simply maximally contracts against an immovable resistance. Garner *et al.* also showed that muscle contraction loaded in either eccentric or concentric contraction elicits a similar amplitude of EMG signal.

REFERENCES

- Basmajain, J. (1967), *Muscles Alive: Their Functions Revealed by Electromyography*, Baltimore: The Williams and Wilkins Company.
- Bigland, B. and Lippold, O.C., "The Relationship between Force, Velocity and Integrated Electrical Activity in Human Muscles", *London J. Physiol*, Vol. 123, pp. 214–24.
- Enoka, R. (1996), "Eccentric Contractions Require Unique Activation Strategies by the Nervous System", *J. Appl. Physiol*, Vol. 81(6), pp. 2339–46.
- Grabiner, M. and Owings, T.M. (2002), "EMG Differences between Concentric and Eccentric Maximum Voluntary Contractions are Evident Prior to Movement Onset", *Exp. Brain Res.*, Vol. 145, pp. 505–11.
- Kossev, A. and Christova, P. (1998), "Discharge Pattern of Human Motor Units During Dynamic Concentric and Eccentric Contractions", *Electroen Clin Neuro*, Vol. 109, pp. 245–55.
- Laidlaw, D., Bilodeau, M. and Enoka, R.M. (2000), "Steadiness is Reduced and Motor Unit Discharge is More Variable in Old Adults", *Muscle Nerve*, Vol. 23, pp. 600–12.
- Seniam (1999), "European Recommendations for Surface Electromyography", *Roessingh Research and Development*, Enschede, Holland.

Dr. Amar Kumar

Assistant Professor, Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Gwalior

Dr. Satpal Yadav

Assistant Professor, Lakshmibai National Institute of Physical Education, Guwahati